

Survey on the stakeholders needs from an Early Warning System

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Survey Context

This survey, developed under PARC Task 8.2, is designed for stakeholders of Early Warning Systems (EWS) or other early response systems dealing with chemical threats. Its purpose is to gather insights that will enhance our understanding of stakeholders' expectations and needs related to an EWS.

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC, <https://www.eu-parc.eu/>), an EU-wide research and innovation partnership, aims to develop next-generation chemical risk assessment to protect human health and the environment. It supports the European Union's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and the European Green Deal's "Zero pollution" ambition with new data, knowledge, methods and tools, expertise, and networks. Task 8.2 specifically contributes to the development of the EC's Early Warning and Action System (EWAS), as outlined in the Chemicals Strategy. This task focuses on identifying potentially hazardous chemicals, particularly emerging concerns, to provide early risk assessments and management insights.

Please ensure you allocate sufficient time to accurately complete this survey, as your input is crucial for advancing our understanding of EWS and enhancing future risk assessments.

Data management

The collected information will be treated confidentially according to the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The pseudonymised data will be processed by the Task 8.2 partners.

Consent

Do you confirm that you have thoroughly reviewed this information and consent to the utilization of the provided information for project-related purposes, including project reports, scientific articles, presentations, and dissemination among partners, as outlined in the terms mentioned above?

- Yes
- No

Deadline for completion: You may save your entries and continue later, but be sure to submit them before **30 April 2025**.

If you have any questions, please contact:

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Thank you for taking the time and focus to complete this survey

1. General information

* 1.1 Are you a partner in PARC?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

1.1.1 In which of the WPs of PARC are you involved as a scientist?

(Multiple choices)

- WP1: Coordination and management
- WP2: A common science-policy agenda
- WP3: Synergies, collaborations, and awareness
- WP4: Monitoring and exposure
- WP5: Hazard assessment
- WP6: Innovation in regulatory risk assessment
- WP7: FAIR data
- WP8: Concepts and toolboxes
- WP9: Building infrastructural and human capacity

* 1.2 In which type of organisation do you work?

- Academia
- Research Institute
- Government agency / regulatory body
- Risk assessment body
- National reference laboratory
- Other

* Please specify

*** 1.3 Your organization's field(s) of work.**

(Multiple choices)

If you are working at a large institute, university or agency, please specify for the unit or division that you are working.

- Chemical sciences
- Data sciences (e.g. modelling)
- Epidemiology
- Healthcare (e.g. medicine, nursing)
- Microbiology
- Nutrition
- Public (Environmental) Health
- Risk / Health Impact Assessment
- Social Sciences
- Toxicology
- Earth sciences
- Environmental sciences
- Other

*** Please specify**

*** 1.4 Which is your specific working area?**

(Select all that apply)

- Analytical chemistry
- Biochemistry
- Chemical products (e.g. polymers, nanomaterials, etc)
- Drugs
- Environmental monitoring and/or evaluation (including, for instance, for the water framework directive)
- Exposure assessment
- Food/Feed Safety
- Hazard characterisation/Hazard assessment
- Human biomonitoring
- Medicinal products
- Microbiology
- Occupational monitoring
- Organic/inorganic chemistry
- Regulation of chemicals
- Risk characterisation/ Risk assessment
- Toxicokinetics (PBPK, QSARs, etc)
- Toxicology (in vitro, in vivo, human)
- Other

*** Please specify**

*** 1.5 What organizational level are you working at?**

(Please specify the highest level if the role may vary over time.)

- Upper management (unit/division head or above)
- First-line management (group/division manager if division is smallest organizational unit)
- Principal investigator
- Researcher
- Regulatory officer
- Administration
- System administrator/technical staff
- Post-doctorate researcher
- Graduate student
- Other

*** Please specify**

*** 1.6 Which specific sources of emerging chemical threats are you interested in within your organization?**

(Multiple choices)

- Biotechnology and Nanotechnology
- Environmental: Air samples/air monitoring
- Environmental : Soil
- Environmental: Water
- Environmental: Biota
- Environmental: Human biomonitoring
- Food & Feed
- Industrial Processes
- Medicinal products & drugs
- Occupational
- Personal care products
- Waste water (municipal, off-site/household, or industrial)
- Waste Management and Recycling (except for waste water)
- Other

*** Please specify**

*** 1.7 Does your institution/organization regularly collect data for chemical substances that are not covered by legislation or for chemicals that have no maximum levels (e.g. legislation on food contaminants, pesticide residues, veterinary drug residues, water framework directive)?**

- Yes, monthly
- Yes, annually
- No
- I don't know

*** 1.8 Have you, in your organization, established screening or monitoring of chemical substances not covered by legislation or without set limit values in order to identify chemical risks (are you presently screening for Chemicals of emerging concern*)?**

**Chemicals of Emerging Concern (CECs) refer to substances that have been identified as potentially harmful to human health or the environment but are not yet fully regulated or monitored by existing laws or standards.*

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

*** 1.9 Have you ever needed to receive or access early warnings about emerging chemical threats?**

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

*** 1.9.1. In which specific situations have you recognized the need for an early warning system (EWS)?**

*** 1.10 How important is it for your organization to receive “early warnings” for chemicals?**

- Very important
- Somehow important
- Not important
- It depends
- I don't know

2. Familiarity with Early Warning System (EWS)

An introduction to the PARC Early Warning System

[Information to stakeholders on general outline of the PARC EWS.pdf](#)

2.1 Are you aware of the existence of any Early Warning System (EWS) at the following levels?

If yes, please specify the system. If not aware of an EWS in any levels, please indicate N/A.

Note: An early warning system may be called something else than an early warning system, such as a rapid alert system. An EWS, for the purpose of this questionnaire, could be any system designed with the intention of providing an alert concerning a chemical risk in a timeframe sufficient to facilitate action to protect the environment or human health. The EWS could be expert-based, computational/data driven, based on chemical or biological tests, etc... More information on the proposed PARC EWS is available in the information sheet provided together with the questionnaire.

	Indicate the EWS
Regional or state level (ie Bundesländer) level	
National level	
European level	
International level	

*** 2.2 Do you consider the output information from an EWS in your work?**

This question is to investigate whether you, in your role, receive alerts or information from an EWS or if you take part in reports, bulletins, newsletters or other outputs from the EWS.

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

*** 2.2.1 If yes, how?**

- New threats or chemicals for targeted research
- Monitoring or data collection
- Toxicological studies
- Risk assessment
- Other

*** Please specify**

*** 2.3 Do you have professional experience with any of the Early Warning System(s) (EWS) you mentioned above?**

This question serves to investigate if you are an active part of an EWS, for instance by providing expert input, chemical analysis, toxicity tests, etc.

- Yes
- No
- I don't wish to answer

2.3.1. Please specify the EWS per level.

If no experience in one level, please indicate N/A

	Indicate the EWS
National level	
European level	
International level	

2.4 What is usually the nature of your involvement in the Early Warning System (EWS)?

- Data provider (input of data)
- Analysis and assessment of input data
- Recipient of EWS outcome
- Other

*** Please specify**

2.5 Please describe a past early warning alert you have responded to.

The purpose of this question is to get a very short description of an early warning.

2.5.1 What kind of actions have you taken in response to the early warning signal you mentioned above?

- Conducted further research
- Informed policy changes
- Adjusted monitoring practices
- I don't know
- Other

* Please specify

2.6 Please indicate the name of the Early Warning System(s) you are currently working on.

2.6.1 Please indicate the scope of the Early Warning System (1).

2.7 How often have you experienced that the Early Warning System (EWS) that you are engaged in is effective in addressing chemical threats?

Please rate on a scale from 1 to 5, with 1 being not effective and 5 being very effective.

- 1 - Rarely
- 2 - Seldom
- 3 - Sometimes
- 4 - Often
- 5 - Very often

2.7.1 Why? Give a brief description

2.8 Which methods are you currently using for the identification of “signals” in the Early Warning System (1)?

(Multiple choices)

- Expert knowledge (e.g Stakeholder surveys)
- Chemical screening e.g. non-target analysis
- Results from effect-based methods (this could be in-vitro assays or in-vivo assays. It can also be explained as organelle, cell-based or organism based tests).
- Trend analysis
- Text mining
- Social media monitoring
- Vigilance systems regarding adverse outcomes from human exposure to chemicals

- Occurrence data
- Patent analysis
- Trade and industry reports
- Read-across
- QSAR
- Other

* Please specify

Do you have any other comment?

2.9 What kind of signals/information do you usually receive in the Early Warning System (1)?

(Multiple choices)

- New substance with properties of concern (e.g. toxicity, bioaccumulation)
- Unexpected levels of a substance
- Increased incidents of human health problems
- Ecological effects
- Alerts from different sources or databases
- Trends in data, for instance abundance, effects, ...
- Detection of a substance at an undesirable location (e.g. pristine ecosystems)
- Other

* Please specify

2.10 What are the main challenges you face with the Early Warning System (1)?

(Multiple choices)

- Technical challenges (e.g. inconsistent signals for known chemicals, identification of unknown-unknown chemicals)
- Data availability and quality
- Monitoring technologies (variation in sensitivity, accuracy, and cost-effectiveness)
- Complexity of chemical mixtures
- Regulatory frameworks
- Interdisciplinary collaboration
- Resource constraints
- Response mechanisms (e.g. emergency protocols, regulatory actions)
- Communication and public awareness
- International cooperation
- Outlining actions
- I don't know
- Other

* Please specify

3. Expectations of an Early Warning System (EWS)

* 3.1 How often would you prefer to get input from an Early Warning System (EWS)?

(multiple choices)

- In real-time monitoring
- Periodic updates - monthly
- Periodic updates - once per year
- Event-driven alerts (for instance contamination, mass mortality,.....)
- I don't know
- Other

* Please specify

* 3.2 How would you prefer to get input from an Early Warning System (EWS)

(Multiple choices)?

- Digital newsletter
- Website with information on new emerging risk chemicals
- E-mail with information you have signed up for
- Tailored information channels depending on the level of risk and information
- I don't know
- Other

* Please specify

* 3.3 Are you open to receiving potentially uncertain alerts from an Early Warning System (EWS)?

For example, notifications (indications concerning) about chemicals that have not been definitively identified but are increasing in prevalence or concentration?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

* 3.3.1 If yes, which level of uncertainty would be acceptable for you concerning the output from an Early Warning System (EWS)?

(See figure below describing possible ways of indicating levels of certainty)

A scale of accepted uncertainty, from 1 (not accepted – very high uncertainty) to 5 (accepted – very low uncertainty)

*** 3.4 Which sources of information or techniques do you think are valuable for further evaluation or “amplification” in an Early Warning System (EWS), suitable for detection/ identification of potential chemical hazards?**

(Multiple choices)

This question pertains to the tools used to evaluate a signal.

- Environmental monitoring
- Human biomonitoring
- Food contaminants
- Consumer products
- Effect-directed analysis
- Non-targeted screening
- Suspect-screening
- Data analysis techniques to identify patterns and/or trends in databases/data analysis from different sources and integration
- New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) (e.g. Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA))
- Non-Animal Technologies (NATs) (e.g. organ on chip)
- Computational modeling tools to predict the properties of the chemical substance (e.g. persistence, mobility, bioaccumulation)
- Computational models to predict the toxicity of the chemical substance
- I don't know
- Other

*** Please specify**

*** 3.5 What kind of information are you expecting from an Early Warning System (EWS)?**

(Multiple Choices)

- Physiochemical Properties
- Structural Information
- Occurrence Data
- Geographic Information
- Temporal Information (e.g. Concentration trends, Prediction of fate and transport, Real-Time Data)
- Exposure levels or environmental concentration
- Environmental Impact
- Toxicological Data
- Health Risks
- Regulatory and Compliance Information
- New Chemical Structures (e.g. read-across data)
- Other

* Please specify

3.6 Please indicate the significance of the following types of information in an Early Warning System (EWS)

(1 not important at all – 5 extremely important)

	1	2	3	4	5
* Detection of a new chemical structure	<input type="radio"/>				
* Increasing occurrence of a specific chemical in a given environmental compartment	<input type="radio"/>				
* Increased detection frequency of a signal suspected to come from a specific chemical	<input type="radio"/>				
* Measured effect, for instance, hormone disruption, in a specific group of samples without a known cause for the effect	<input type="radio"/>				
* Increased use of a chemical identity in text data such as news items, scientific literature, patents	<input type="radio"/>				
* Regulations covered by observed chemical	<input type="radio"/>				
* Detection of a chemical in an unexpected location (e.g. pristine ecosystems, food items)	<input type="radio"/>				
* Predicted fate and transport of chemicals	<input type="radio"/>				
* Predicted environmental exposure	<input type="radio"/>				
* Predicted human exposure	<input type="radio"/>				
* Predicted internal exposure based on metabolic transformation	<input type="radio"/>				
* Predicted effects of detected chemical (hazard endpoints, endocrine disrupting activity, genotox, skin sensitization, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				

Other, please specify

*** 3.7 How could the delivery of "early warnings" be improved to better meet your needs?**

(Multiple Choices)

- Accuracy/quality of the information or data provided
- Speed or frequency
- Comprehensiveness
- Tailored information (for instance PTM, predicted effect on specific endpoints, etc)
- Inclusion of uncertainty analysis
- I don't know
- Other

* Please specify

4. Final Comments

Please include here any general remarks or comments you would like to add regarding the Early Warning System (EWS) that was not addressed above.

End of the survey

Thank you for taking the time and focus to complete this survey.

End of the survey
